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Empirical Evidence of the Determinants of Internal Audit Effectiveness in the Educational Institutions

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ABSTRACT

This study empirically examines the determinants of internal audit effectiveness in the Educational Institutions. This study focuses on the effect of independence of internal audit, internal audit quality, management support, relationship between internal and external audit and risk management on the internal audit effectiveness. The study utilized survey research design to collect the data from 150 respondents from various universities, polytechnics and monotechnics. The data collected is subjected to the following diagnostic tests including multicollinearity test, normally test and outlier assessment to ensure fitness of the data. Descriptive statistics and multiple regression are used in analyzing the data collected and the findings reveal that that independence of internal audit, internal audit quality and management support have positive and significant influence on the internal audit effectiveness while the relationship between internal and external audit have positive but non-significant effect on the internal audit effectiveness in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Therefore, this study conclude that independence of internal audit, internal audit quality and management support are key factors that determine internal audit effectiveness. Based on the conclusion this study recommend that internal audit department in the Nigerian Tertiary Institutions should be allow to operate independently of the management and any undue pressure that will affect their level of independence. The management of tertiary institutions in Nigeria should also provide all the necessary resources and support needed by the internal audit department in order to discharge their responsibilities effectively.

Keywords: internal audit effectiveness, internal audit quality, Educational Institutions

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Internal audit plays a crucial role in promoting good governance of public funds. The internal audit department has been utilized as a means of reducing opportunistic behaviors, minimize external monitoring cost, checkmate fraud risks, reduce risk, enhance control risks and used for other non-financial related activities in an entity. Keeping enough resources at the maximum level and right amount at all the time helps management to attain the target objectives of the organizations and improves the quality of financial management of government activities or projects (Rudhani, Vokshi & Hashani, 2017).

The importance of internal audit has significantly increased recently, most especially in the area of risk management in an organization. The increasing rate of fraud, bankruptcy and accounting scandals has attracted the attention of practitioners, professionals and researchers on internal audit function as a critical factor contributing to the effectiveness of an organization (Al-shbail & Turki, 2017). Internal audit unit will enhance an organizational value through the provision of management and operational control on many issues (Abu-Azza, 2012). Nevertheless, some literature has shown that the results of the effectiveness of internal audit unit may not be the same always (Abuazza et al., 2015). This statement is

true most especially in developing countries like Nigeria where an organization may not have an idea of the cost and benefit of internal audit practices as it is in the developed economy.

Many frauds related cases in government organization indicate a lot of weakness in the effectiveness of internal audit function. The public sector is the biggest and major provider of job opportunities and organizations that share public funds for various activities via budget, such organizations requires functional or workable mechanism to supervise the process of utilization and disbursement of public funds in accordance with the laid down provisions of the law (Rudhani, Vokshi & Hashani, 2017).

Prior research reported that there are few studies on the effectiveness of internal audit and observed that the effectiveness of internal audit assessment is significant and important in knowing the factors that affect internal audit effectiveness and quality (Alzeban & Gwillian, 2014). Moreover, some studies have considered the combination of various factors that contribute to the effectiveness of internal audit. For example, Al-shbail and Turki (2017) studied the combination of independence of internal audit, scope of internal audit, management support of internal audit, and cooperation of internal and external auditors. While, Azzali and Mazza (2018) examine factors that include relationship between internal and external auditors and process of internal audit. Similarly, Musah, Gapketor and Anokye (2017) investigated the size of internal audit unit, competence of internal audit unit, independence of internal audit unit, management support of internal audit unit and relationship between internal and external auditors. Rudhani, Vokshi and Hashani (2018) examined factors like quality of internal audit, competence of internal audit, independence of internal audit and management support of internal audit. Moreover, Badara and Siti (2014) considered risk management, performance measurement, audit experience, cooperation between internal and external auditor. However, these prior studies have not considered the joint effect of internal audit independence, management support, relationship between internal and external auditors, quality of internal audit and risk management as antecedent variables in relation to internal audit effectiveness.

Judging from the negative impact of fraud, misappropriation of funds and assets in public sector organization and the existing gap in the literatures, the objective of this study is to fill in the gap by presenting the results of an empirical studies into the perception and opinion of internal auditors and accountants in the government tertiary institutions in Nigeria concerning the effectiveness of internal audit in improving performance. Thus, this study examines the effectiveness of internal audit functions in educational institution in Nigeria.

In addition to the introduction, section two review literatures on the internal audit, audit independence, management support, relationship between external and internal auditors, risk management, quality of audit and the empirical review of previous studies. Section three briefly discuss the research methodology used in the study. Section four detailed the presentation and discussion of statistical results and provide a comparative analysis of the two groups of respondents. Lastly, section five discussed the summary and conclusion of the study.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual and Empirical Review

An entity can only be effective if the results of its operational activities are in accordance with the stated objectives of the entity. Solomon et al. (2019) defined internal audit as an independent and objective functions in form of assurance and consulting activities or functions, designed to enhance or add value and improve organizational operation. Rudhani, Vokshi and Hashani, (2017) considered internal audit as the investigation of accounting records to check and ascertain their correctness and its compliance with organizational policies, relevant laws, professional statements and accounting standards. This shows that internal audit unit is responsible for auditing financial transactions of an organization that are recorded in books of accounts for the purpose of correcting errors, detecting and preventing fraud. Ege (2021) further states that the quality of internal audit mitigate fraud risks, reduces external monitoring cost, earning management, minimize risk and other opportunistic behaviors within the organization despite the size and improve organization performance. Internal audit evaluates the operation of an organization in order to strengthen and enhance the governance mechanisms including strategic risk management and the

organization's internal control system (Solomon et al. 2019). It is an independent unit designed to assess and improve the effectiveness of internal control, risk management and governance process (Adamu and Mahmoud, 2023). An effective audit process is essential in the public sector because it protects the interests of the citizens and enhances the ability to hold public officials accountable and strengthening governance process.

Most prior studies on internal audit effectiveness presented mixed results. To start with Solomon et al. (2019) examine the determinants of internal audit effectiveness in four potential factors that include independence, management support, quality of audit work, career and development, and concluded that the internal audit effectiveness is an important concept that has been under studied, and concentration of researches was geared mostly to the study of external audit instead of internal audit. For instance, Rudhani, Vokshi and Hashani (2017) considered four factors that contributed to internal audit effectiveness like audit quality, competence of internal audit team, independence of internal audit and management support in Kosovo, and found out that all the four factors had significant and positive relationship with internal audit effectiveness. In addition, audit quality was discovered to be the most influential factor to internal audit effectiveness. In the same vein, Musah, Gakketer and Anokye (2018) examined four determinants of internal audit effectiveness in Ghana that include size of internal audit unit, competence of internal audit unit, independence of internal audit unit, management support of internal audit unit and relationship between internal and external auditors and discovered a significant positive and strong relationship between these factors and effectiveness of internal audit. Thus, the study concluded that management support is the most significant factor in determining the effectiveness of internal audit.

Similarly, Bouthach and Taouab (2023) empirically evidence of the main factors influencing the effectiveness of internal audit in public sector in Morocco, namely independence, competence, management support and the use of the function as a career opportunity. Using a quantitative data collected through a questionnaire survey of a sample of 43 auditors selected from public administrations. The results shows that the independence of the internal audit, competence and the support of senior management contribute to improving the effectiveness of the internal audit. Aminu, Isah, Ahmad (2022) also investigates the determinants of internal audit effectiveness of public sector organizations operating in the North Eastern Nigeria using primary data obtained from 148 questionnaires administered on internal auditors. PLS-SEM technique of multiple regressions was utilized for data analysis. The finding of this study revealed that the quality of internal audit, competence and management support have positive and significant influence on internal audit effectiveness while independence of internal audit and information and communication technology conversely showed negative and insignificant influence.

Thu Trang et al. (2022) examined four factors affecting internal audit effectiveness in Vietnam, namely internal audit independence, competence, management support and quality of internal audit. Using a survey design data were collected from 144 respondents. The results revealed that internal audit independence and management support positively influence the effectiveness of the internal audit while competence and internal audit quality does not have influence on the internal audit effectiveness. Azzali and Mazza (2018) took a different dimension and considered factors such as audit size, listing and big4. Their results show positive relationship between audit size, listing, big4 and the effectiveness of internal audit in Italy. Moreover, Al-shbail and Turaki (2018) investigated the relationship between independence of internal audit, scope of internal audit, management support of internal audit, cooperation of internal and external auditors and internal audit effectiveness, and conclude that all the factors contributed positively to the success of internal audit efficiency. Dewi, Azam and Yusoff (2019) found internal control system, quality of financial statement, human resource competence positively influences financial accountability in Indonesia. This shows that the findings from the previous studies on independence of internal audit, management support, relationship between internal and external auditor, risk management and quality of internal audit is still mixed and inconclusive.

2.2 Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses Development

According to DiMaggio and Powell (1983) institutional pressures and a desire to compare with other organizations in a similar environment, organizations tend to adopt similar characteristics through three mechanisms of isomorphism. Prior studies have utilized institutional theory and explain the pressures being applied in internal audit research. Mihret et al (2010) had noted that the influence of government through imposition had been substantial on organizations in the establishment of internal audit function as a result of coercive pressures, mimetic pressure and normative pressure to ensure conformity with standards and regulations. Aminu, Isa and Ahmad (2022) argued that there is a positive relationship between compliance with standards and regulations and achievement of organizational objectives. Therefore, this study utilized Institutional theory examine the determinants of internal audit effectiveness in the educational institutions in Nigeria.

Independence of Internal Audit

Internal audit independence allows internal audit to make professional judgments without being unduly influenced by others. It is a fundamental principle of the auditing profession and is essential for maintaining the credibility and reliability of audits (Adamu Damagun, 2023). Independence of an audit is always related with external audit. For the auditor to work objectively, auditing work has to be independent from the organization to be audited to avoid undue influence and interference. Independence of an auditor may influence effective auditing and activities and fasten the competition. This has to do with allowing the auditor access at all time of important and relevant documents without being afraid, which will in turn lead to the production of an objective report (Purnomo, 2017).

Professional bodies and auditing standard boards have accorded great importance on independence of an internal auditor nowadays, despite the fact that they are employees of the entity. One of the most essential ingredients or properties of an effective internal audit unit is the independence of internal audit function (Al-Akra et al., 2016; Al-shbail & Turki, 2017; Musah, Gapketor & Anokye, 2018). For instance, Musah, Gapketor & Anokye (2018) states that despite the fact that very few studies have studied the effectiveness of internal audit in relation to independence of an internal audit, the study has reported a significant positive effect of independence of independence of internal audit on internal audit effectiveness in Ghana. Other studies that have posited significant improvement of independence on internal audit effectiveness (Al-Akra et al., 2016; Dellai & Omri, 2016; Purnomo, 2017). Auditors have a responsibility to maintain their independence and to protect the interests of the public by complying the laws, regulations and guidelines that have been issued to ensure that audit is conducted objectively (Ebubechukwu, 2023). Accordingly, this proposed that the following hypothesis:

H1 Independence of internal audit has positive and significant influence on Internal audit effectiveness.

Internal Audit Quality

Auditors experience gives the internal audit unit the opportunity to produce quality results and good recommendations on an audit in an organization. Internal audit is an indispensable key in assisting organizations to reach their objectives. It is an independent, objective assurance and consulting activity designed to add value and improve the effectiveness of an organizational processes such as internal control, risk management, and governance. Therefore, the quality of internal audit is directly related to the organization's financial performance and play an important role in protecting organizations from risks, corruption, safeguarding assets, checking compliance with organizational policy and regulations to enhance the reliability of financial reports (Subhi & Stanisic, 2016; Postula et al., 2020). Accordingly, this study proposed the following hypothesis:

H2 Internal audit quality has positive and significant influence on Internal audit effectiveness

Management Support

The perception of internal audit functions in an entity can be attributed on the management support, support received, funding, levels of overlap between internal audit understanding regulations governing the activities of internal audit training and development and appreciation of internal audit role by other activities in the organization (Usang & Salim, 2016). Prior studies have argued that management support is very vital to the achievement of internal audit function or unit. For instance, Al-shbail & Turki (2017)

argued that management support is a prerequisite for effective internal audit function, management should know that internal audit function is as important as any other activity undertaken in an entity. Internal audit function may likely fail if the commitment of management to make it functional is not there.

Musah, Gapketor & Anokye (2018) discovered management support as an effectiveness of internal audit function is the most important determinants of the success of an internal audit department. Internal auditor can get enough resources with the support of top management responsibilities to carry out their functions by providing regular training and education and development and the recruitment of qualified and quality staff (Alzeban & Sawan, 2013). Adamu and Mahmoud (2023) add that lack of management support is a barrier to internal audit effectiveness in the public sector. The manner in which senior management demonstrate their support likely provides an important signal of the role and value of internal auditing throughout the organization (Abdulaziz and David 2014). This support in turn empowers the internal audit department to execute its duties and fulfil its responsibilities effectively. Accordingly, this study proposed the following hypothesis:

H3 Management support has positive and significant influence on Internal audit effectiveness

Relationship Between Internal and External Auditors

The internal and external auditors work together with the aim of realizing a common objective of the organization. Internal and external auditor's relationship has to do with the areas such as exchange of information, coordination, planning, sharing opinions and reports to perform standardize audit devoid of duplication of function (Musah, Gapketor & Anokye, 2018). Thus, prior studies have indicated that when there is no cooperation between internal and external auditors it will impair the quality of audit performed in government organization. Coordination and cooperation between internal and external auditors have long been seen as important to the audit which benefits the organization and external stakeholders. For Instance, such coordination and cooperation include joint planning and exchange of information, opinions and reports to facilitate higher-quality audits and prevent unnecessary duplication of work.

Previous studies indicate that appropriate cooperation increases the economy, efficiency, and effectiveness of audits and helps management provide a high-quality public service. The absence of cooperation between internal and external auditors is frequently identified as a factor impairing the quality of both forms of audit in the public sector in developing countries (Adamu and Damagan 2023). Abdulaziz and David (2014) found that management support was the second most important determinant of internal audit effectiveness within the Malaysian public sector, after sufficiency of the auditing staff. They indicated that with support from management, internal audit recommendations would likely be implemented and the internal audit would be well-resourced in terms of number of staff and budget. Therefore, this study proposed the following hypothesis:

H4 Relationship between internal and external audit has positive and significant influence on Internal audit effectiveness

Risk Management

Risk management is the procedure of identifying risk and its management in order to achieve the entity goals and enhance the effectiveness of internal audit. Thus, effective management of risk help organizations to achieve their goals, and it being considered as an important part of good corporate governance. Thus, government organizations should consider risk management as a matter of priority to assist in the realization of their goals.

Risk management is usually performed in the private sector organization (business sector) in other to manage the risk that will hinder the organization from achieving its goals. Recently, with the increasing and complexity of activities in the public sector, there is also a need to conduct risk management. According to COSO "it is a process affected by an entity board of directors, management and other personnel applied in strategic settings and across the enterprise, designed to identify potential events that may affect the entity manage risk to be within its risk appetite, and provide reasonable assurance regarding the achievement of entity objective." Alternatively, risk management is a process, structures and culture that are channel toward arriving at potential opportunities and managing adverse effects at the same time (Purnomo, 2017).

Previous studies on risk management are centered on the role of internal audit in risk management, with the exception of the studies by Purnomo (2017) and Badara (2014) which considered the effect of risk management on effectiveness of internal audit. Hence, this study is going to examine risk management and the effectiveness of internal audit in educational institutions in Nigeria. Many studies have shown that risk management have a crucial role to perform in the achievement of internal audit objectives (Vasile & Mitran, 2012; Purnomo, 2017). For instance, Purnomo (2017) conducted a study and found that risk management significantly influences internal audit effectiveness which means that the ability of the public sector organizations to minimize their risk level is positively related to internal audit effectiveness. Therefore, this study proposed the following hypothesis:

H5 Risk management has positive and significant influence on Internal audit effectiveness

3.0 RESEARCH METHOD

The study used survey research design. Survey research is selected because it provides visible evidence concerning the perception and experience of the respondents with regards to the subject matter. The population of the study consist of all the tertiary educational institution in the North- Eastern Nigeria. The stratified sampling method is employed and the tertiary educational institutions is divided into three; universities, polytechnics and monotechnics. Followed by purposive sampling technique to select the sample respondents. All the variables of the study were derived from past studies. Items used in the questionnaire for measuring internal audit effectiveness, independence, management support, relationship between internal and external auditors, risk management and quality of internal audit has been derived and adopted from past studies. Thus, items used to measure the dimension of independence of internal audit, internal audit quality, management support, relationship between internal and external auditors and risk management were adopted from the works of Musah, Gapketor and Anokye (2018) and Rudhani, Vokshi and Hashani (2017) while internal audit effectiveness was adopted from Al-shbail and Turki (2017) and Musah, Gapketor and Anokye (2018). Data collected from the questionnaire is based on five-point Likert scale from strongly agreed (5), agreed (4), undecided (3), disagree (2) and strongly disagreed (1).

The total of 150 questionnaires were distributed via research assistants; 145 questionnaires were returned out of which 142 were retained and utilized for analysis in this study. Data analysis was carried out quantitatively using descriptive statistics and multiple regression technique. Multiple regression technique is used because it gives accurate estimate of the magnitude of the effect of the independence variables on the dependent variable (Hair et al. 2017, Gujarati and Porter 2025). The unit of analysis for the study is tertiary educational institutions, where responses were collected from the staff of the finance (bursary) and internal audit department of the tertiary institutions. The data collected is subjected to diagnostic check to ensure compliance with the assumptions of multivariate analysis. Therefore, normality test, multicollinearity test and assessment of possible outlier have conducted before the multiple regression analysis.

The multiple regression model utilized in the analysis is as follows:

$$IAE = f(IIA, IAQ, MS, IE, RM) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

$$IAE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IIA + \beta_2 IAQ + \beta_3 MS + \beta_4 IE + \beta_5 RM + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Where:

- IAE = Internal audit effectiveness
- β_0 = represent the fixed intercept,
- β_1-5 = the coefficient of the independent variables
- IIA = Independence of internal audit
- IAQ = Internal audit quality
- MS = Management support
- IE = Relationship between internal and external audit
- RM = Risk management
- ϵ = the error term

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The diagnostic tests conducted have not indicate any multicollinearity problem because the variance inflation factor (VIF) of all the independent variables is less than 10 which reveal the absence of multicollinearity (Hair et al. 2017, Gujarati and Porter 2025), the p-value from the normality test is higher than 5% which indicate the residuals have not deviated from a normal distribution. Similarly, the result of the outlier test using both multivariate and univariate analysis have not indicated any issue of outlier in the data collected. Thus, descriptive statistics and regression analysis is conducted and results is presented below.

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistic of the independent variables of the study is presented in table 1 which shows the mean value and standard deviation of the variables and the number of the respondents that participated in the survey.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Variables of the Study

Variables of the Study	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Internal Audit Effectiveness	4.03	0.81	142
Independence of Internal Audit	4.21	0.75	142
Internal Audit Quality	4.08	0.53	142
Management Support	3.85	0.62	142
Relation b/w Internal and External Audit	3.91	0.56	142
Risk Management	4.05	0.72	142

Source: Author's Compilation generated Using SPSS (2025)

Table 1 provide descriptive statistics of the research variables and mean score is above the midpoint score on the scale of one to five where (1) is the extent that respondent strongly disagree, and (5) is the extent that the respondent strongly agreed which suggest a positive. The result show that the effectiveness of internal audit (IAE) is strongly determine by the explanatory variables with an average score of 4.03. The independence of internal audit (IIA) has the highest mean score (4.21) while management support (MS) has the lowest mean score (3.85). Further, the standard deviation of the respondent is evenly distributed around the mean score of all the variables.

Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis of the variables shows the level of association between the variables and presence of multicollinearity among the independent variables. The result of the correlation analysis is presented which is presented in table 2. According to Hair et al (2017) and Gujarati and Porter (2025) that a correlation coefficient higher than 0.8 indicate the presence of multicollinearity among the variables of the study. The result of the correlation analysis as presented in table 2 shows that IIA, IAQ and MS have positive and strong association with dependent variable while IE and RM have positive and moderate association with the dependent variable. IIA has the strongest association with the internal audit effectiveness (IAI=0.751). This result shows that the explanatory variables have the possibility of influencing internal audit effectiveness.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix of the Variables of the Study

Variables	IAE	IIA	IAQ	MS	IE	RM
IAE	1					
IIA	0.751	1				
IAQ	0.674	0.721	1			
MS	0.712	0.683	0.614	1		
IE	0.536	0.692	0.567	0.753	1	
RM	0.561	0.515	0.738	0.726	0.675	1

Source: Author's Compilation generated Using SPSS (2025).

Regression Results

The regression result on the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable (Internal audit effectiveness) of the study is presented in table 3. The results show the level of influence of each latent variable on the internal audit effectiveness of tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Table 3: Regression Result (Dependent Variable: Internal Audit Effectiveness)

Variables	Standardized		Sig.	Decision
	Beta	t-stat		
Internal Audit Independence	0.211	4.21	0.001	Accept
Internal Audit Quality	0.231	3.67	0.000	Accept
Management Support	0.310	3.26	0.005	Accept
Relationship b/w Internal & External Audit	0.184	1.58	0.172	Reject
Risk Management	0.318	4.01	0.003	Accept
R-Square		0.621		
Adjusted R-Square		0.583		
Standard Error of the Estimate	0.461			

Source: Author's Compilation generated Using SPSS (2025)

The R-square value is 0.583 shows the proportion of the dependent variable that is explain by the explanatory variables. The value of the R-square indicates that 58% of the determinants of internal audit effectiveness is explained by the independent variables (IAI, IAQ, MS, IE, RM) of the study while the remaining 42% is explain by other factors not capture by the research model of the study. The result shows that independence of internal audit have positive and significant influence on the internal audit effectiveness ($\beta = 0.211$ and $p = 0.001$). This result has provided a support for accepting hypothesis 1 which state that IAI positively and significantly influence internal audit effectiveness. This result means that independence of internal audit is an important factor that determine the IAE, therefore, internal audit should be allowed to carry out their duties and responsibilities independently without any undue pressure or interference from the management in order to have an effective and efficient internal audit. This finding is consistent with Adamu and Dmagun (2023), Aminu, Isa and Ahmad (2022) and Solomon et al. (2019) among others.

The internal audit quality and management support also have positive and significant influence on the internal audit effectiveness ($\beta = 0.231$) and ($\beta = 0.310$) respectively. Management support to the internal audit department also drives effectiveness in the internal audit because the department requires resources and competent man power to discharge it duties and responsibilities. Therefore, there need for maximum support from the management of Nigeria Tertiary Institutions to the internal audit department in term of providing the required resources, facilities and competent staff that will carry out the audit functions efficiently. This management support will improve the quality of the internal audit work leading to an effective internal audit service in these Tertiary Institutions. This finding is similar to the results of Adamu and Damagun (2023) and Aminu, Isa and Ahmad (2022) among others. Thus, the finding has provided evidence for accepting hypothesis 2 and 3. However, the relationship between internal and external audit has positive but non-significant effect on the internal audit effectiveness ($\beta = 0.184$ and $p = 0.172$). Although, there is need for a good relationship between the internal and external audit which increases the internal audit effectiveness but it is not a significant factor that influences internal audit effectiveness. This provides evidence for rejecting hypothesis 4 which state that the relationship between internal and external audit significantly influence the internal audit effectiveness. Finally, the result reveals that risk management positively and significantly influence the internal audit effectiveness ($\beta = 0.318$ and $p = 0.003$). Risk is unavoidable in the operation of an organization but the ability to management determines the success of every organization. Therefore, risk management is a key factor that determine the effectiveness of internal controls in operation leading to an effective internal audit.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study empirically examines the determinants of internal audit effectiveness in the educational institutions in Nigeria. Five (5) explanatory variables have been examined (independence of internal audit, internal audit quality, management support, relationship between internal and external audit and risk management) and findings show that independence of internal audit, internal audit quality and management support have positive and significant influence on the internal audit effectiveness while relationship between internal and external audit have positive but non-significant effect on the internal audit effectiveness in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Therefore, this study conclude that independence of internal audit, internal audit quality and management support are among the key factors that determine internal audit effectiveness. Based on the conclusion this study recommend that internal audit department in the Nigerian tertiary institutions should be allow to operate independently of the management and any undue pressure that will affect their level of independence. The management of tertiary institutions in Nigeria should also provide all the necessary resources and support needed by the internal audit department in order to discharge their duties effectively.

Moreover, the internal audit department should be provided with modern technology and skills that will assist them in undertaking their audit functions. The support from the management will improve the quality of internal audit functions leading to an effective internal audit. The smooth relationship between internal and external auditors positively influences the effectiveness of internal audit. Thus, the internal and external auditors are expected to have cordial understanding and work together in order to improve the internal audit effectiveness.

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